

The role of family support and internal locus of control in entrepreneurial intention of vocational high school students

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between family support and internal locus of control with entrepreneurial intention among grade XII students attending Muhammadiyah 3 Vocational High School. From 172 grade XI students attending the school, 93 were selected to participate in the study. This study used a cluster-sampling technique. The data was collected using the entrepreneurial intention scale, the family support scale, and the internal locus of control scale. Multiple regression techniques were used to analyze the data on SPSS 19.0. The results indicated very significant positive relationship between family support and internal locus of control with entrepreneurial intention, family support with entrepreneurial intention, and internal locus of control with entrepreneurship intention. Thus, it can be inferred that the contribution of internal locus of control to entrepreneurial intention is more dominant than family support's contribution.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In 2018, Central Bureau Statistics [1] released that 5.13% of the Indonesian population, or 6.87 million people, are in open unemployment. Based on the educational background, vocational high school graduates contribute to the highest unemployment rate at 8.92%. The number of unemployed vocational high school graduates is particularly high due to an imbalance between vocational high schools' education curriculum and the number of work demand from the industrial and service sectors [2]. That problem is contrary to the expectation of establishing vocational high schools which is to create work-ready graduates [3]. One way to reduce unemployment is the development of entrepreneurship [4]. In addition to bringing a solution for unemployment, entrepreneurship is also a measure of economic growth and development in a country [5]. The development of entrepreneurial interest and skills is crucial; thus, there is a need for entrepreneurship education to interest students' interest in developing a business enterprise, otherwise known as entrepreneurial intention [6].

Entrepreneurial intention is individuals' desire to carry out entrepreneurial activities by developing new business through existing business opportunities [7]. Entrepreneurial intention allows individuals to have a positive attitude and behavior regarding various risks in entrepreneurship [8]. Individuals who possess entrepreneurial intention can deliberate about and develop new business ventures [9]. Entrepreneurial intention consists of four dimensions, namely: 1) Desire, which is the internal drive in the form of interest and desire to start a business; 2) Preferences, which is the sense that entrepreneurship attainment is a

necessity; 3) Plans, which is a desire to start a business in the future; 4) Behavior expectancies, which is the possibility for entrepreneurship followed by a goal of starting a business.

Students with high entrepreneurial intention have a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship [10], strive to turn entrepreneurial intention into entrepreneurial behavior [11], demonstrate entrepreneurial activities [12], are ready to face entrepreneurship risks [13], and can establish a business venture in the future [14]. Conversely, students with low entrepreneurial intention tend to have unfavorable perceptions about the various risks that one must face in entrepreneurship [15], are confused when faced with entrepreneurship opportunities [16], and give up easily when encountering entrepreneurial obstacles [17]. In a broader sense, low entrepreneurial intention lead to lower employment [18].

Various factors influence entrepreneurial intention, one of which is social support [19]-[21]. Social support is the perception or experience of being loved, cared for, valued, and supported by others [22]. Among the various type of social support, one that has been found to influence entrepreneurial intention is family support [23]. Family support is defined as a family's behavior and attitude in accepting its family members, which can take emotional, informational, and instrumental support [24]. Support can provide physical and psychological comfort in dealing with stress [25] and can also take motivation, advice, information, and real help [26].

Sarafino and Smith [27] suggested that family support includes several aspects, namely: 1) Emotional support, which involves expression of feelings, empathy, and attention to an individual, allowing one to feel comfortable, loved and cared for; 2) Appreciation support, which is a positive evaluation towards other's ideas, feelings, and performance, manifested through expressions of respect for family members; 3) Instrumental support, involving family members as a source of aid and unswerving supporting, can take the form of supervision, fulfillment of personal needs, as well as financial assistance or help in completing a task; 4) Informative support, which can take the form of information, advice, guidance, and feedback on how to solve a particular problem.

Supportive families tend to increase togetherness over time and become sources of support for each other [23]. Family support in the entrepreneurial context can take the form of information as well as help in acquiring or providing venture capitals, especially financial capitals [28]. Family support eases individuals in deciding to start a business, providing a boost of confidence in their abilities [29], as well as a positive appraisal of their decisions [30].

In addition to family support, another factor that can influence entrepreneurial intention are personality factors [31]. One dimension of personality that influences entrepreneurial intention is an internal locus of control [32]. Internal locus of control is the belief that every event that occurs to oneself is caused by factors that exist in his or herself [33]. Individuals who believe that their actions result in life happenings tend to believe that: they can control the results of their efforts [34], a particular action can produce the expected results [35], and one can determine his or her destiny and achievements [36], [37].

Individuals who have an internal locus of control are characterized by their: 1) Ability, defined as the mastery of a skill or the potential to master a skill, which is believed to determine the outcome of their success and failure; 2) Effort, meaning that individuals tend to be optimistic, have a never-give-up attitude and try their best to control behavior so that they can realize their desires [38].

Individuals who have a clear vision of their future will strive to realize their desires for entrepreneurship [39], [40]. Also, strong self-control leads individuals to believe that their quality of life is self-determined; thus, the willingness to work hard for success [41]. In the entrepreneurial context, individuals with an internal locus of control have a higher chance of undertaking entrepreneurial activities and starting new businesses [31]. Based on the above explanation, the relationship between family support, internal locus of control, and entrepreneurial intention can be illustrated through as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The relationship between family support, internal locus of control and entrepreneurial intention

Based on the description of the problem background, which is also supported by the results of previous studies, the researcher intended to explore further the relationship between family support and internal locus of control with the entrepreneurial intention grade XII students of Muhammadiyah 3 Vocational High School.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Population and sample

The population of this study was 172 grade XII students of Muhammadiyah 3 Vocational High School. The total class is seven classes. The sample of this study were 93 students. This study used a cluster random sampling technique conducted by randomizing students from each class.

2.2. Instruments

Data collection was conducted using psychological scales as research instruments, namely the entrepreneurial intention Scale, the family support scale, and the internal locus of control scale. Tentama and Abdussalam [42] developed the entrepreneurial intention scale by referring to the dimensions of entrepreneurship intention according to Gelderen, *et al.* [43], namely desires, preferences, plans, and behavior expectancies. The Entrepreneurial Intention Scale used the Likert Scale to measure its intended variable. Examples of the scale of entrepreneurial intention are: "I aspire to become an entrepreneur," "I like things related to the world of entrepreneurship," and "I plan to expand my knowledge about independent business enterprise."

The family support scale is developed based on aspects of family support suggested by Sarafino and Smith [27], namely emotional support, appreciation support, instrumental support, and informative support. The scaling model used in the family support scale is the Likert Scale. An example of a family support scale includes: "my family respects my opinions," "my family provides the facilities that I need," and "my parents provide the best advice when I am in trouble."

The internal locus of control scale is constructed based on the dimensions of internal locus of control proposed by Lefcourt [34], namely ability and effort. The scaling model used in the Internal Locus of Control Scale is the Likert Scale. Example of items in the Internal Locus of Control Scale includes: "my ability to determine my success," "doing the task with maximum effort will help complete the task quickly," and "I am able to resolve occurring conflicts."

2.3. Validity and reliability

A pilot testing of the instruments was conducted with 60 students. Results of the pilot testing indicate of instruments that the entrepreneurial intention scale obtained a reliability coefficient (α) of 0.868. The item discriminant power (corrected item-total correlation) ranged between 0.447 to 0.707. The study produced 12 valid and reliable items. Secondly, the family support scale obtained a reliability coefficient (α) of 0.957. The item discriminant power (corrected item-total correlation) ranged between 0.450 and 0.831. The study produced 28 valid and reliable items. Finally, the pilot testing results on 60 students showed that the internal locus of control scale obtained a reliability coefficient (α) of 0.860. The item discriminant power (corrected item-total correlation) ranged between 0.352 to 0.677. The study produced 14 valid and reliable items.

2.4. Data analysis

Data analysis was conducted using parametric statistical analysis. Multiple regression analysis was conducted on SPSS 19.0 for Windows to examine the relationship between family support and internal locus of control with entrepreneurial intention. The assumption tested before analysis are the normality test, linearity test, and multicollinearity test.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Assumptions testing

3.1.1. Normality test

Based on the normality test seen in Table 1, the significance value of each variable are: entrepreneurial intention at 0.129 ($p > 0.05$), family support at 0.100 ($p > 0.05$), and internal locus of control at 0.072 ($p > 0.05$). Based on the normality test, it can be concluded that all variables in this study are normally distributed.

Table 1. Results of normality test

Variable	Score K-SZ	Sig.	Annotation
Entrepreneurial intention	0.083	0.129	Normal
Family support	0.084	0.100	Normal
Internal locus of control	0.088	0.072	Normal

3.1.2. Linearity test

Linearity test aims to determine which two variables have a significant linear relationship. Based on Table 2, the linearity test results on entrepreneurial intention and family support acquired an F of 0.451 and p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a linear relationship between the two variables. The relationship between entrepreneurial intention and internal locus of control obtained F of 0.919 and p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a linear relationship between entrepreneurial intention and linear internal locus of control. Based on these results, it can be concluded that the data in this study meet the linearity requirements.

Table 2. Results of linearity test

Variable	F linearity	Sig.	Annotation
Entrepreneurial intention and family support	0.451	0.000	Linear
Entrepreneurial intention and internal locus of control	0.919	0.000	Linear

3.1.3. Multicollinearity test

Based on the multicollinearity test results in Table 3, family support and internal locus of control obtained a VIF value of 1.883 ($VIF < 10$) and a tolerance value of 0.531 ($\text{tolerance} > 0.1$). Thus, there is no multicollinearity or low correlations between family support and internal locus of control.

Table 3. Result of multicollinearity test

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Annotation
Family support	0.531	1.883	No multicollinearity
Internal locus of control	0.531	1.883	No multicollinearity

3.2. Hypothesis testing

The data analysis results in Table 4 shows that there is a relationship between family support and entrepreneurial intention with $r = 0.37$ ($p < 0.01$), meaning that partially, there is a positive and very significant relationship between family support and entrepreneurial intention. The relationship between internal locus of control and entrepreneurial intention obtained $r = 0.504$ ($p < 0.01$), meaning that partially, there was a positive and very significant relationship between internal locus of control and entrepreneurial intention.

The results of the multiple linear regression analysis as shown in Table 5, simultaneously, family support and internal locus of control have a very significant relationship with entrepreneurial intention in students of Muhammadiyah 3 Vocational High School. These results indicate that the first hypothesis is accepted, thereby inferring that family support and internal locus of control can predict entrepreneurial intention. Simultaneously, the two independent variables contribute 28% to entrepreneurial intention, while other factors possibly influence 72%. Other factors that can influence entrepreneurial intention include the need for achievement and subjective norms [44], sense of worthiness as entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship barriers [45], educational support [21], entrepreneurship education [46] and entrepreneurial exposure [47]. The contribution of family support and internal locus of control to entrepreneurial intention is 7.28% and 21.1%. Thus, it can be inferred that the contribution of internal locus of control to entrepreneurial intention is more dominant than family support's contribution.

Table 4. Partial hypothesis test

Variable	r	Sig.	Criteria	Annotation
Family support and entrepreneurial intention	0.371	0.000	$p < 0.01$	Very significant relationship
Internal locus of control and entrepreneurial intention	0.504	0.000	$p < 0.01$	Very significant relationship

Table 5. Simultaneous hypothesis testing

Variable	R	R Square	Sig.	Criteria	Annotation
Family support and internal locus of control towards entrepreneurial intention	0.529	0.280	0.000	p<0.01	Very significant relationship

The results indicate that the second hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is a very significant relationship between family support and entrepreneurial intention in Muhammadiyah 3 Vocational High School students. This result is in line with previous research which also found that family support predicts entrepreneurial intention [48]-[51]. Students have a higher entrepreneurial intention when they have the support needed to establish an enterprise [52].

Family support is crucial, particularly for students whose wants are strongly influenced by family support, both emotionally and financially [23], [53]. Students who have high emotional support tend to have stronger entrepreneurial aspirations due to the belief that their families can support them during the various cycles of entrepreneurship, which are often unpredictable [54]. Students who receive from the families' support in the form of information regarding entrepreneurship have relatively vast knowledge leading them to become more confident in entrepreneurship [55], [56].

The results also indicate that the third hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is a very significant relationship between internal locus of control and entrepreneurial intention in Muhammadiyah 3 Vocational High School students. This result is in line with previous research, which also found that internal locus of control can predict entrepreneurial intention [57]-[60]. Students with a high internal locus of control believe that their lives are self-determined, thereby leading them to have had the confidence to determine the career path they desire, by being better and bolder in starting business ventures [60].

Students who believe that they can strive to achieve their desires will attempt to realize their entrepreneurial intention [61] and do things that are considered to bring entrepreneurial success [32]. Belief in this context consists of students' belief of becoming entrepreneurs and the belief that the entrepreneurship results can be controlled through various efforts [62]. Through these beliefs, students subsequently build a stronger desire for entrepreneurship.

The findings of this study are different from previous studies. The results of previous studies on entrepreneurial intentions indicate that the factors that influence entrepreneurial intention are entrepreneurship education [63], self-efficacy and family support [64], subjective norms and hardiness [65] and entrepreneurial training [66]. This research is expected to complement previous research to make it more comprehensive. This study implies that students who have entrepreneurial intention require internal and external factors to realize entrepreneurial behaviours. Students must attempt to develop their internal locus of control because it is a dominant internal factor that influences entrepreneurial intention. However, internal factors must also have the backing of external factors, namely family support to encourage the formation of students' entrepreneurial intention to its maximum.

4. CONCLUSION

To be able to apply their learning outcomes upon graduation, the entrepreneurial intention has, in recent times, become a crucial need for students of Muhammadiyah 3 Vocational High School. Students need to pay attention to both external and internal factors in developing entrepreneurial intention, namely family support and internal locus of control. Simultaneously, there is a very significant relationship between family support and internal locus of control with entrepreneurial intention in students. Partially, there is very significant positive relationship between family support and entrepreneurial intentions in students, as well as very significant positive relationship between internal locus of control and entrepreneurial intention in students. Family support and internal locus of control contribute to entrepreneurial intention. The most dominant contribution is internal locus of control as an internal factor.

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